

Experimental

5,7,8-Trimethoxy-2,3-dimethylchromone (IIa) :

A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy-propio-phenone² (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 ml) and freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) was heated at 180° in an oil bath for 10 hr. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted compound. It was then washed with water and dried. The product was dissolved in benzene and the solution was run through a short column of alumina. The compound was eluted with benzene. Evaporation of the solvent left the residue, which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 162°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 63.52; H, 6.01. C₁₄H₁₆O₅ requires : C, 63.63; H, 6.11%).

5,7,8-Trimethoxy-3-methylflavone (IIb) :

A mixture of 3,4,6-Trimethoxy propiophenone (1 g.), benzoic anhydride (4 g.) and freshly fused sodium benzoate (5 g.) was heated at 200° in an oil bath for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was boiled with water and filtered. The product was treated with aq. sodium hydroxide solution (30 ml, 5%) for about 30 min. The insoluble compound was filtered, washed with water and dried. The compound, in methanol, was passed through a short column of alumina and eluted with methanol. Evaporation of the solvent gave the residue, which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 164°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found : C, 69.55; H, 5.52. C₁₉H₁₈O₅ requires : C, 69.93; H, 5.71%).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. E. Gellert, Wollongong University College, Wollongong, Australia, for I.R. Spectra, Prof. S. Sethna, for taking interest in the work and Dr. S. S. Lele for microanalysis of the compound.

References

1. P. F. WILEY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4329.
2. W. BAKER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 665.
3. Y. A. SHAIKH and K. N. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (Communicated).
4. S. K. MUKHERJEE, T. R. SESHADRI and S. VARADARAJAN, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1952, **35A**, 82.

Thin Layer Chromatographic Studies of Some Substituted Thioureas

H. L. PANGARKAR & A. P. JOSHI

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur

Manuscript received 26 March 1973; accepted 7 June 1973

PAPER chromatographic studies of some substituted thioureas have been reported¹⁻⁴ but thin layer chromatographic (TLC) studies seem to have received little attention. The present work was carried out on TLC of some substituted thioureas.

Experimental

The thioureas were prepared by the usual methods⁵, purified by crystallization from suitable solvents. Nitrogen and sulphur contents in the compounds were estimated by Kjeldahl and Messenger's method respectively, and were well in agreement with the theoretical values. The melting points also agreed with the reported values.

Silica gel G was used as an adsorbent and small glass plates were used as carriers. Silica gel slurry was prepared in methanol and the plates were coated with the adsorbent by immersion technique. The plates were allowed to dry and the layers were activated by keeping the plates in an oven at 150° for 2-3 hr. The dried plates were marked with a pin for the spot line.

The substances were dissolved in ethanol. These solutions were then spotted on the plates with a 10 λ pipette. The spot had a diameter between 2 to 5 mm. After the spot had dried, the plates were kept in an inclined position in a chamber containing the solvent. The chamber was closed with a glass cover to saturate the chamber atmosphere with solvent vapour.

When the solvent had travelled sufficiently along the plates, they were taken out and the solvent front was marked. The time taken by the solvent to travel along the plate was 30 to 40 min. The temperature of the chamber was kept constant during the experiment. The spots on the plates were visualized by two different methods : (i) by exposing the dried plates to iodine vapour whence thioureas appear as dark brown spots; (ii) by using Grote's reagent⁶; the dried plates are sprayed with this reagent and heated in an oven for 30 min, thereupon the thioureas appeared as deep blue spots. The R_f values were then calculated and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. R_f VALUES OF THIOUREAS IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS

Compounds	A	B	C	D	E	F
phenyl thiourea	0.63	0.98	0.26	0.72	0.69	—
diphenyl thiourea	0.97	0.91	0.40	0.77	0.76	—
dibenzyl thiourea	0.93	0.82	0.35	0.79	0.97	—
<i>o</i> -tolyl thiourea	0.37	0.96	0.41	0.97	0.97	0.70
<i>m</i> -tolyl thiourea	0.39	0.94	0.37	0.98	0.93	0.84
<i>p</i> -tolyl thiourea	0.59	0.96	0.35	0.81	0.94	0.83
<i>o</i> -methoxy phenyl thiourea	0.59	—	0.26	0.74	0.94	0.93
<i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl thiourea	0.66	—	0.78	0.81	0.90	0.94

A—water saturated chloroform

B—benzene : ethanol (1 : 1, V : V)

C—chloroform : carbon tetrachloride (1 : 1, V : V)

D—ethanol

E—dioxane

F—ethyl acetate : carbon tetrachloride (1 : 1, V : V).

Solvents A, C, E can be used for the separation of phenyl thiourea from diphenyl thioureas while A, B, C, E can be used for the separation of phenyl thiourea from dibenzyl thiourea. Solvents E and F can give separation of *o*-tolyl and *m*-tolyl thiourea while A, D, E and F can be used for the separation of *o*-tolyl from *p*-tolyl thiourea. *o*-Methoxy and *p*-methoxy phenyl thiourea can be best separated in solvent C alone.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. R. H. Sahasrabudhey, Head, Chemistry Department, Nagpur University, Nagpur for encouragement.

References

1. C. D. BELLS and E. CELON, *J. Chromatog.*, 1967, **31**, 77.
2. L. M. KOVINS and N. K. ROZHKOVA, *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, **70**, 74092y.
3. A. KJAER and K. RUBENSTEIN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1953, **7**, 528; *Nature*, 1953, **171**, 840.
4. M. NANDA, R. B. DAS KANUNGO, B. C. DASH and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 251.
5. A. I. VOGEL, A text book of practical organic chemistry including qualitative organic analysis. The English Language Book Society and Longman, Third Edition, p. 643.
6. E. STAHL, *Thin Layer Chromatography, A Laboratory Handbook*. George, Allen and Unwin Ltd., London, 1969.

Isomorphous Replacement of Hydroxyl Group by Fluoride Group in Kaolinite and Bentonite

R. K. SHAH & B. N. OZA

Department of Chemistry, University School of Sciences, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-9

Manuscript received 24 December 1971; accepted 7 May 1973

THE clay minerals kaolinite and bentonite were studied for isomorphous replacement of hydroxyl ion by fluoride ion¹⁻¹⁴. Kaolinite has as many as 6 OH groups on the surface of the crystal lattice and in the case of bentonite (montmorillonite) comparatively less hydroxyls are present on the crystal surface. Experimental data obtained, are present on the crystal surface. Experimental data obtained, are presented in Tables 1 and 2, and shown graphically in diagrams 1 to 6.

Diagram 1 indicates changes in *pH* on adding increasing proportions of 0.1 *M* solutions of different fluoride salts to normal kaolinite and bentonite and H-kaolinite and H-bentonite.

Diagrams 2 to 6 indicate liberated hydroxyl ion proportion with time factor.

TABLE 1. ACTION OF HYDROFLUORIC ACID ON DIFFERENT CLAYS

Sample No.	SiO ₂ /R ₂ O ₃	Boiling for ½ hr. wt. loss v/v		
		1% HF	5.0% HF	10% HF
2	1.62	47.6	—	77.7
12	1.21	52.0	72.0	85.5
14	2.38	54.0	64.3	65.4
16	1.59	38.8	60.9	61.3
18	2.19	35.4	42.8	54.3
30	1.17	47.1	94.2	94.2
33	2.92	41.4	86.7	90.6
35	1.10	51.0	95.5	98.0
36	1.10	49.8	92.8	94.4
Kaolinite	1.08	52.7	98.7	98.8
Bentonite	—	46.5	88.7	91.0

Discussion

The effect of different concentrations of hydrofluoric acid on clay was studied. The data (Table 1) show that 10% HF will cause as much as 98% kaolinite and 91% bentonite to enter into solution. This indicates complete breakdown of the crystal lattice of the clay minerals. The higher degree of disruption of the crystal lattice in the case of kaolinite with hydrofluoric acid may be explained on the ground that it may be due to preferential extraction of Aluminium from the lattice, leaving an intermediate silica phase which dissolves to form fluo-silicic acid.

The possible reaction may be :

Theoretically with an increase in the concentration of hydrofluoric acid, only 86% dissolution is possible, but in practice dissolution in the case of kaolinite reaches 98%. To explain this high value, it is believed that the following reaction may also be simultaneously taking place :

TABLE 2. EFFECT OF KF (NEUTRAL SOLUTION) ON OH⁻ LIBERATION

	0.1M		0.5M	
	Boiling for 2 hr.	Without boiling 6 days	Boiling for 2 hr.	Without boiling 6 days
	g/100 g.			
Bentonite	1.050	1.038	2.100	1.220
Kaolinite	0.680	0.510	3.120	1.660

The comparative behaviour of interaction of fluorides with kaolinite and bentonite is shown by changes in *pH* when normal kaolinite, H-kaolinite, normal bentonite and H-bentonite are reacted with 0.1 *M* HF, 0.1 *M* NaF and 0.1 *M* NH₄F (Diagram 1).